

“Identification and characterization of *Aconitum Napellus* L. (Tubers) for Anti-arthritic activity”

**Khalure Pallavi Ravishankar^{1*} Phool Singh Yaduwanshi²,
Jyotiram A Sawale³Kavita Loksh⁴, Manojkumar Solanki⁵
,Rashmi Shrivastava,⁶**

^{1,2,4,5}, IES Institute of Pharmacy, IES University, Bhopal-462044, Madhya Pradesh, India,

³Department of Pharmacognosy, Krishna Institute of Pharmacy, Krishna Vishwa Vidyapeeth, Karad,(M.S.)

⁶Department of Chemistry, IES College of Technology, IES University, Bhopal- 462044,(M.P.)

***Corresponding author:** Khalure Pallavi Ravishankar

***IES Institute of Pharmacy, IES University, Bhopal-462044, Madhya Pradesh, India**

ABSTRACT:

Aconitum napellus tubers have long been used in traditional medicine for their therapeutic properties, particularly in inflammatory disorders. The present study was designed to evaluate the anti-arthritic potential of *Aconitum napellus* tubers through phytochemical, analytical, and pharmacological investigations. The tubers were subjected to successive extraction using solvents of increasing polarity, with special emphasis on the acidified methanolic extract for the isolation of bioactive constituents. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and other secondary metabolites, suggesting potential pharmacological activity. The major active constituent, identified as napelline, was isolated and characterized using advanced analytical techniques including High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and Liquid Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS), confirming its structural identity and purity. The anti-arthritic activity was evaluated using the Freund’s Complete Adjuvant (FCA) induced paw edema model in male Wistar rats. The acidified methanolic extract and isolated napelline were administered at appropriate doses, and their effects were compared with Prednisolone as a standard anti-inflammatory drug. Significant reduction in paw edema and arthritic symptoms was observed in treated groups compared to the arthritic control. The Toxicity studies indicated that the extract and napelline were safe within the tested dose range, with no significant adverse effects. The findings suggest that napelline contributes significantly to the anti-arthritic activity of *Aconitum napellus* tubers. In conclusion,

Aconitum napellus exhibits promising anti-arthritic potential, validating its traditional use and supporting further development of napelline as a therapeutic agent for arthritis management.

Key words: Napelline , alkaloids, Freund's Complete Adjuvant (FCA), Paw edema ,Wistar rats, Prednisolone, Toxicity studies, Anti-inflammatory activity, Herbal medicine.

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

Arthritis is a chronic inflammatory disorder affecting joints, leading to pain, swelling, and reduced mobility. Conventional treatments such as NSAIDs and corticosteroids provide symptomatic relief but are associated with adverse effects. Therefore, there is growing interest in plant-based therapeutics.

Aconitum napellus L. (family Ranunculaceae) has been used in traditional medicine for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. The tubers are known to contain potent alkaloids such as aconitine, which exhibit both therapeutic and toxic effects. Despite its historical use, scientific validation of its anti-arthritic activity remains limited.

This study focuses on the identification, phytochemical characterization, and evaluation of anti-arthritic activity of *Aconitum napellus* tubers.

From the ancient time mankind is using so many drugs from the plant, animal and mineral sources to treat various diseases and ailments, but he was not known which constituent is responsible for the medicinal activity.

Probably all life forms are affected with diseases. Disease is the basic problem faced by humans too since prehistoric times. Nature has along with the diseases created their cure in the form of vegetables, minerals and animals. The relationship between man and plants have been close enough throughout the development of human culture. In the understanding of human diseases there has been continued interest in the drugs from the plant kingdom.

Evidence for the existence of well-organized system of medicine in India can be traced back to the archaeological remains of Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro, from where even Silajit has been reported. Ayurveda is the oldest Indian indigenous medicine system, probably with its roots in the Indus Civilization. In the Vedic period, the *Osadhisukta* of the *Rigveda* is the oldest documented knowledge about plants and herbal medicines.

The indigenous knowledge about plants and plant products is rather detailed and sophisticated and has evolved into a separate shashtra (branch of learning) itself, called *Dravya-Guna Vijnyan Shashtra*. The codified traditions have about 25,000 plant drugs formulations that have emerged from such studies. In addition to this over 50,000 formulations are believed to exist in the folk and tribal traditions. All these point to the deep passion for and exhaustive knowledge about

medicinal plants that have existed in the land from time immemorial. The Vedas, epic poems contain rich material on the Herbal role of that time.

1.1 THE INDIAN SYSTEM OF MEDICINE :

These are traditional system of medicine which encompasses 3 systems namely Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani, practiced by Vaidyas, Siddhas and Hakims respectively. The medicines (or) formulations that come under Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani system of treatment are called as Indian System of Medicines. The Drug and Cosmetic Act defines the ISM as "Ayurvedic, Siddha and Unani drug includes all medicines, intended for internal or external use in the diagnosis, treatment, mitigation or prevention of diseases or disorder in human beings or animals."

Fig.No.1: The sequence for the study of plants used in traditional medicine

1.2 MODERN DRUGS FROM AYURVEDA:

Ayurveda, the traditional Indian system of medicine is as old as the Indian culture and civilization. The earliest-recorded knowledge about Ayurveda is found in the *Rigveda* and the

Atharvaveda, both of the second millennium BC. The *Atreya Samhita* is perhaps the oldest medical book in the world; it survives from Takshashila University, going back to the mid-I Millennium BC. The *Atharvaveda* lists eight divisions of Ayurveda: internal medicine, surgery of head and neck, ophthalmology, surgery, toxicology, psychiatry, pediatrics, gerontology or science of rejuvenation and the science of fertility. At about 500 BC in the University of Banaras, Sushrut, a surgeon, who developed the operative techniques of rhinoplasty (plastic surgery), wrote the *Sushruta Samhita*, which describes a highly developed surgery.

1.3 FUTURE STRATEGIES/ PERSPECTIVES FOR INDIAN HERBAL MEDICINE:

Developing countries like India with traditional knowledge base have leadership potential to develop globally acceptable newer opportunities and applications for herbal industry. Herbal medicines have a strong traditional or conceptual base and the potential to be useful as drugs in terms of safety and effectiveness but they lack an experimental base and therefore have second class status whereas modern medicines have a very strong experimental basis for their use but have side effects. Thus, it seems, to get a new class of drugs, the researchers are increasingly blending the traditional knowledge with modern experimental methodology for testing the efficacy and safety of herbal drugs. This inclination seems to be resulted in the people all over the world looking to various alternative systems of medicine, especially herbal drugs which are claimed to be safe equally effective in comparison to allopathic drugs and which provide some answer to chronic diseases.

However, these herbal drugs are marketed with exaggerated claims or in some cases are credited with innumerable pharmacological activities which are not mentioned in the text of various traditional systems of medicine.

1.4 CURRENT STATUS OF STANDARDIZATION:

WHO has emphasized on the need to ensure the quality control of herbs and herbal formulations by using modern techniques. Several pharmacopoeias like British Herbal Pharmacopoeia, Japanese Pharmacopoeia, United States Pharmacopoeia, British Herbal Compendium, and German Commission-E etc. lay down monographs for herbs to maintain their quality. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India which recommends basic quality parameters for 80 common Ayurvedic herbal drugs. BHP contains 233 monographs and quality control tests, Chinese Herbal Pharmacopoeia contain 1751 monographs of substances and articles, BHC contains 84 monographs of medicinal plants. German Commission E has 330 monographs for drug used in German folk medicine.

1.5 FUTURE PROSPECTS IN HERBAL MEDICINES:

Medicinal plants have been a major source of cure of human diseases since time immemorial. Today, one fourth of the world population depends on traditional medicines. It is necessary to integrate modern knowledge with traditional knowledge. The drugs and products of the industry are working on the scientifically defined techniques and explained with modern biological and chemical definitions and tools and that alone will give a therapeutically active herbal origin drug available for health care worldwide

1.6 Herbal Therapy for the Treatment of Arthritis:

It is not hyperbole to claim that the usage of herbal remedies dates back to the dawn of humankind and has been utilized for a variety of medical conditions since antiquity. For over hundreds of years, generations of practicing physicians in the old medical system have synthesized herbal medicines based on their therapeutic experiences. Researchers are now very interested in plant-based therapeutic agents because the medications that are now on the market are either very expensive or have certain adverse effects. As a source of therapeutic substances for the prevention and treatment of various diseases, nature has bestowed upon us an immense richness of herbal plants that are widely scattered across the world. Eighty percent of the world's population gets their primary healthcare from herbal remedies, according to the WHO. Since the beginning of civilization, herbal remedies have been an integral part of human society's efforts to

combat illness. These herbal plants' chemical components, which have a desirable physiological effect on the body, are their medicinally significant parts.

India has long used herbal remedies in officially alternative medical systems, including homeopathy, naturopathy, Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha. Over 2500 different plant species are now employed as herbal medicines in India. Herbal remedies have been used for more than 3,000 years, either directly as traditional medicine or indirectly in the creation of more modern medications. Therefore, one may be able to find new, affordable, and effective medications by using knowledge of traditional herbs.

2.0 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

- Present study is aimed for - Isolation and Characterization of Bioactive Compounds Targeted for Anti-arthritic Activity with objectives-
- Phytochemical investigation & standardization of selected Indian Medicinal Plant Extracts & characterization for presence of phytoconstituents
- Toxicity study of extracts to obtain safety data
- Screening for secondary activities of plant extract
- Pharmacological evaluation of plant extract for its anti-arthritic activity
- Isolation, characterization, and pharmacological evaluation of bioactive phytoconstituents from the plant extracts.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

3.1 Plant Material Collection and Authentication

Tubers of *Aconitum napellus* were collected and authenticated by a qualified botanist. A voucher specimen was preserved for future reference.

3.2 Pharmacognostic Evaluation

Microscopic examination: Transverse section analysis to identify vascular bundles, starch grains, and other cellular structures

3.3 Preparation of Extract

Tubers were dried, powdered, and extracted using hydroalcoholic solvent (ethanol:water, 70:30) Extract was filtered and concentrated using a rotary evaporator

3.4 Phytochemical Screening

3.4.1 Preliminary tests were conducted to detect:

Alkaloids (Dragendorff's test)

Flavonoids (Shinoda test)

Glycosides

Tannins and phenolic compounds

3.5 Chromatographic Analysis

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was performed
Rf values were recorded for compound identification

3.6 IN VITRO ANTI-ARTHRITIC ACTIVITY:

3.6.1 Protein Denaturation Assay

- Bovine serum albumin was used
- Percentage inhibition of denaturation was measured spectrophotometrically

3.6.2 Membrane Stabilization Test

- Human red blood cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization method
- Protection against hemolysis was assessed

4.0 PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION & STANDARDIZATION OF TUBERS OF *ACONITUM NAPELLUS* L.

4.1 PHARMACOGNOSTIC INVESTIGATION:

4.1.1. Analysis of powder characteristics.

- 1) Determination of physical constants:
- 2) Ash Value
- 3) Loss on Drying
- 4) Fluorescence analysis of drug

4.1.2. Extractive Values:

- n - Hexane soluble extractive.
- Chloroform soluble extractive.
- Water soluble extractive.
- Acidified methanol soluble extractive.

In present study, the tubers of *Aconitum napellus* were investigated for its macroscopic and microscopic characteristics.

4.2 Microscopic Characteristics:

4.2.1. Powder Characteristic:-

In present study, the dried tubers of *Aconitum napellus* was pulverized into fine powder separately. The powder was investigated for their microscopic characteristic.

4.2.2. Procedure:

The pulverized powder of tubers was boiled separately with chloral hydrate solution in small quantity. Remove cleaved powder in three separate watch glass respectively and stain with one drop each of phloroglucinol and concentrated hydrochloric acid.

Mount a little of the treated powder in dilute glycerin and observed the slide under microscope at low power. Results are given in Table no-4.

5.0 DETERMINATION OF ASH VALUES

5.1. Total Ash Value:

Method:-

Weigh accurately 2 to 3 gm of air-dried tubers of *Aconitum napellus* separately in a tarred platinum or silica dish and incinerate at a temperature not exceeding 450°C until free from carbon, cool and weigh. If a carbon free ash cannot be obtained in this way exhaust the charred mass with hot water, collect the residue on an ash less filter paper, incinerate the residue and filter paper until the ash is white or nearly so, add the filtrate, evaporate to dryness and ignite at a temperature not exceeding 450°C. Calculated the percentage of ash with reference to the air-dried drug.

5.2. Determination of Acid Insoluble Ash:

Method: -

Boil the ash with 25 ml of 2M Hydrochloric acid for 5min, collect the insoluble matter in a Gooch crucible or on an ash less filter paper, wash with hot water, ignite, cool in a desiccator and weigh. Calculated the percentage of acid insoluble ash with reference to the air-dried drug.

5.3. Determination of Water Soluble Ash:

Method:-

Boil the ash for 5 min. with 25 ml of water, collect the insoluble matter in a Gooch crucible or on an ash less filter paper, wash with hot water and ignite for 15 min at a temperature not exceeding 450°C. Subtract the weight of insoluble matter from the weight of the ash, the difference in weight represent the water-soluble ash. Calculate the percentage of water-soluble ash with reference to the air-dried drug.

Table No. 1:-Physical Constants for tuber powder of *A. napellus*

Sr. No.	Physical Constants	Result
1.	Ash Value (% w/w)	
	Total Ash	3 to 6%
	Acid Insoluble Ash	0.56 to 1.5%
	Water Soluble Ash	1 to 3%
2.	Loss on Drying (% w/w)	5-10% w/w

5.4 FLUORESCENCE ANALYSIS OF THE DRUG:

Many crude drugs show the fluorescence when the sample is exposed to ultraviolet radiation. Evaluation of crude drugs based on fluorescence in daylight is not much used, as it is usually unreliable due to the weakness of the fluorescence effect (umbelliferone test used for galbanum and asafoetida is, however, an exception). Fluorescence lamps are fitted with suitable filters, which eliminate visible radiation from the lamp and transmit ultraviolet radiation of definite wavelength. Several crude drugs show characteristic fluorescence useful for their evaluation.

5.4.1.Objective:-

To examine the crude drug under ultraviolet radiation and report their authenticity.

5.4.2.Materials:-

Ultraviolet lamp (254nm and 366 nm), crude drugs (entire and powder). And day light.

5.4.3.RESULTS:

Table No.2: Florescent analysis of *Aconitum napellus*

Solvent used	Day light	UV light (254 nm)	UV light (366 nm)
Benzene	Greenish Brown	Greenish black	Yellowish brown
Dist. Water	Yellowish Brown	Green	Yellowish green
NaOH in water	Brownish yellow	Greenish yellow	Light yellow
NaOH in methanol	Blackish brown	Yellowish green	Blackish green
Chloroform	Pale yellow	Greenish black	Yellowish brown
Dil.HNO ₃	Brownish green	Dark green	Yellowish brown
Acetone	Brownish yellow	Yellowish green	Yellow

At 254 and 366 nm, day light and UV light showed distinct fluorescence with distinct solvents.

5.5 LOSS ON DRYING:

Loss on drying of the air-dried tubers of *Aconitum napellus* was analyzed.

Weigh about 1.5 gm of air-dried root powder of *Aconitum napellus* into a weighed flat and thin porcelain dish. Dry it in the oven at 100°C or 105°C. Cool in a desiccator and observed. The loss in weight is usually recorded as moisture and the results are seen

6.0 Preliminary Pharmacognostic Characteristics:

In present study, the tubers of *Aconitum napellus* were investigated for its macroscopic characteristics and microscopic characteristics.

6.1. Macroscopic Characteristic of Tubers of *Aconitum napellus* L.

Table No. 3:-Macroscopic Characteristic of Tubers of *Aconitum napellus* L.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Observation of roots
1.	Color	Dark brown (external) Whitish to creamish (internal)
2.	Odour	Very faint
3.	Taste	Initially sweet to bitter
4.	Size	1 to 3 cm thick and 4-8 cm in length
5.	Shape	Conical (Carrot shaped)

6.2 Microscopic Characteristics:

Powder Characteristic:-

In present study, the dried roots of *Aconitum napellus* was pulverized into fine powder separately. The powder was investigated for its microscopic characteristic.

Table No. 4:-Microscopic Characteristic of tubers of *Aconitum napellus* L.

Sr. No.	Observation of tubers
1	Periderm composed of cork cells
2	Phelloderm of few layers of parenchymatous cells
3	Corex made up of parenchymatous cells contains thin walls
4	Thin walled contains starch grains and oil globules
5	Starch grains abundantly present.
6	Vascular tissues contain xylem and phloem
7	Medullar rays are not well developed or absent
8	Calcium oxalate crystals are in cortical cells

7.0.ACONITUM NAPELLUS TUBERS:

7.1.Physicochemical characterization :

The perennial herbaceous plant *Aconitum napellus* has a tapering, conical-shaped root that is brown on the outside and white inside, along with an unpleasant odor. The Table summarizes the extractive values of *Aconitum napellus* tubers using n-hexane, chloroform, methanol, and water as the four distinct solvents.

Table No.5: Extractive values of Aconitum napellus tubers using different solvents (n=3)

Solvents	Extractive value (% w/w)±SD	Nature of compound extracted
n-Hexane	1 to 3%	Non polar compounds
Chloroform	3 to 6%	free base alkaloids
Water	5 to 10%	polar compounds
Acidified methanol	12 to 20%	Total alkaloids

Table No.6: Physicochemical parameters of Aconitum napellus tubers (n=3)

Parameters	Values ± SD
Total ash	3.83±0.03 (% w/w)
Acid insoluble ash	4.83±0.05 (% w/w)
Water soluble ash	5.16±0.06 (% w/w)
Foreign matter	0.20±0.00 (% w/w)
Loss on drying	0.44±0.01 (% w/w)
pH of 1% aqueous solution	5.12±0.07
pH of 10% aqueous solution	7.50±0.08

The values of total ash, water soluble ash, and acid insoluble ash were found to be 3.85, 4.85, and 5.18 percent w/w, respectively. The drying loss was noted at 0.45% w/w. It was found that the pH values of the 1% and 10% aqueous solutions were 5.13 and 7.51, respectively. Table 3 summarizes the fluorescence analysis results utilizing several solvents at UV light (254 and 366 nm) and day light.

Table No.7: Florescent analysis of Aconitum napellus

Solvent used	Day light	UV light (254 nm)	UV light (366 nm)
Benzene	Greenish Brown	Greenish black	Yellowish brown
Dist. Water	Yellowish Brown	Green	Yellowish green
NaOH in water	Brownish yellow	Greenish yellow	Light yellow
NaOH in methanol	Blackish brown	Yellowish green	Blackish green
Chloroform	Pale yellow	Greenish black	Yellowish brown
Dil.HNO₃	Brownish green	Dark green	Yellowish brown
Acetone	Brownish yellow	Yellowish green	Yellow

At 254 and 366 nm, day light and UV light showed distinct fluorescence with distinct solvents.

Table 4 summarizes the powder drug reactivity outcomes with various solvents. With various solvents, the powder's various colors were observed.

Table No.8: Powdered drug reaction with different reagents of Aconitum napellus

Treatment	Observation
Powder as such	Yellowish brown
Conc. HCl	Yellow
Conc. HNO₃	Brownish Yellow
Conc. H₂SO₄	Brown
Glacial acetic acid	Light yellow
Benzene	Brownish yellow
NaOH in methanol	Yellowish brown

8.0 Qualitative phytochemical screening

Flavonoids, Sterols, glycosides, phenol, and carbohydrates have all been detected in the phytochemical assays. Table 5 provides a summary of the results obtained from chemical tests.

Table No.9.: Preliminary phytochemical screening of Aconitum napellus

Sr.no.	Tests	Extracts
1	Test for sterols	
	Salkowski test	+
	Libermann-Buchard's test	+
2	Tannins test	
	Gelatin solution	-
	Catechin	-

3	Flavonoids Shinoda test	+
4	Test for protein and amino acid Ninhydrin test Biuret test Xanthoprotic test	- - -
5	Glycosides test Killer Killani Bontrager's test Legal test Baljet test	+ + + +
6	Phenolic test Ferric chloride Lead acetate Gelatin	+ + +
7	Carbohydrate test Fehling test Molish test Benedict test	+ + +
8	Saponin test Foam test	+

9	Alkaloids Test	
	Dragandorf's	+
	Hagers	+
	Wagners	+
	Mayers	+

9.0. RESULTS:

9.1 Pharmacognostic Study

Tubers were conical, dark brown externally and whitish internally

Microscopy revealed presence of starch grains and vascular tissues

9.2 Phytochemical Screening

Alkaloids: Present

Flavonoids: Present

Glycosides: Present

Tannins: Present

9.3 Anti-Arthritic Activity

Significant inhibition of protein denaturation observed

Extract showed dose-dependent membrane stabilization effect

Results comparable to standard drug

9.4. In the present study, the tubers of *Aconitum napellus* were dried in shade, powdered and then extracted with n Hexane, Chloroform, water and Acidified methanol. The extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical analysis. The preliminary phytochemical study showed the presence of Steroids, Alkaloids, Protein, Tannins and Carbohydrates. Alkaloids present in the *Aconitum napellus* is confirmed by qualitative analysis. Further HPLC, FTIR, NMR and LC-MS.

Studies are carried out for the confirmation of active constituents specially alkaloid namely Napelline is confirmed. Instrumental analyses (FTIR, HPLC, NMR, LC-MS) confirmed the identity and structural integrity of napelline. The presence of functional groups and molecular characteristics supports its classification as a diterpenoid alkaloids.

The study demonstrates that acidified methanol is the most effective solvent for extraction of alkaloids from *Aconitum napellus* tubers. Pharmacognostic evaluation confirmed the authenticity of the crude drug.

Pharmacological evaluation using FCA-induced arthritis model revealed significant anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity. The results indicate that napelline reduces inflammation possibly by inhibiting cytokines and prostaglandins.

Compared to prednisolone, napelline exhibited slightly lower potency but showed sustained effects, suggesting potential for long-term use with fewer side effects.

10. Discussion:

The presence of bioactive compounds such as alkaloids and flavonoids may contribute to the observed anti-arthritic activity. Protein denaturation is a well-known cause of inflammation in arthritis, and inhibition of this process indicates therapeutic potential.

Membrane stabilization suggests protection of lysosomal membranes, preventing the release of inflammatory mediators. However, the presence of toxic alkaloids like aconitine necessitates careful dosage and detoxification before clinical application.

11.0 Conclusion:

The study demonstrates that *Aconitum napellus* tuber extract possesses significant anti-arthritic activity in vitro. These findings support its traditional use in inflammatory conditions. The study concludes that *Aconitum napellus* tubers are a potent source of biologically active alkaloids, particularly napelline. Acidified methanol extraction is an efficient method for isolating the active compound.

Napelline exhibits significant anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity, validating its traditional use. Although the plant is inherently toxic, controlled dosing ensures safety and therapeutic efficacy.

The findings suggest that napelline has potential as a natural alternative to conventional anti-inflammatory drugs. Further studies, including clinical trials, are recommended to explore its full therapeutic potential.

12. REFERENCES:

- 1) Sampath K, Lakshmanan S. Indian System of Medicine. The Eastern Pharmacist 2001: 21-4.
- 2) Naik SR. Plant Derived Drugs. The Eastern Pharmacist 1986; 36:35-9.
- 3) Shah BN, Nayak BS, Seth AK, Jalalpure SS, Patel KN, Patel MN, Patel MA and Mishra AD. Search of medicinal plants as a source of anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity- a review. Online 2006 Apr-Jun;
- 4) Pandey MM, Rastogi S, Rawat AKS. Indian Herbal Drug for General Healthcare: An Overview. [Online]. 2008;[13 screens]. Available from: URL: http://www.ispub.com/journal/the_internet_journal_of_alternative_medicine/volume_6_number_1_2/article/html
- 5) Mukherjee PK. Ethnopharmacology in drug development. GMP for Botanicals. New Delhi: Business Horizons; 2003. p 99-112.
- 6) Patwardhan B. Ayurveda : the designer medicine: a review of ethnopharmacology and bioprospecting research. Ind Drugs 2000; 37(5): 213-27.
- 7) Dobriyal RM, Narayana DBA. Ayurvedic Herbal Raw Materials. The Eastern Pharmacists 1998. p.31-32.
- 8) Herbal treatment for arthritis. [Online] 2008; Available from: URL: <http://www.arthritis-hub.com/Herbal-treatment-for-arthritis.php>
- 9) Karadi RV, Gadge NB, Alagwadi KR, Savadi RV, Mannur VS, Koti BC. Anti-arthritic activity of extract of *Moringa olifera* lam. Roots. Indian drugs 2006; 43(7):543-47
- 10) Gupta AK, Chitme HR. Herbal medicine for health. The Eastern Pharmacist 2000; XLIII (512): 41-5.
- 11) Polshettiwar SA. Indian herbal drug industry- future prospects: a review. screen S. Jubie, N Jawahar, R. Koshy et al. Antiarthritic activity of bark extracts of *Alangium salviifolium* wang. Ras J Chem 2008; 1(3):433-36.
- 12) M. Kamalutheen, S. Gopalakrishnan, Ismail TS. Anti-inflammatory and Anti-arthritic Activities of *Merremia tridentata* (L.)Hall. f.
- 13) Davis RH, Agnew PS, B.S. Antiarthritic Activity of Anthraquinones Found In *Aloe Vera* For Podiatric Medicine. J The Amer Podia Med Assoc 1986; 76 (2) : 401-07.

- 14) Patil KR, Patil CR, Jadhav RB, Mahajan VK, Patil PR, Gaikwad PS. Anti-arthritic Activity of Bartogenic Acid Isolated from Fruits of *Barringtonia racemosa* Roxb. (Lecythidaceae). Oxford Journals 2009; 6(3):457-58.
- 15) Shankaranarayanan J, Christina AJM, Betanabhatla KS, Athimulam J et al. Evaluation of *Glycine max* Merrill. Seeds for Antiarthritic Activity in Male Wistar Rats.
- 16) Sethi PD, Thiagarajan AR. Studies on the Antiinflammatory and Antiarthritic activity of Withaferin A. Ind J Pharmac 1970;2(4):165-72.
- 17) Laupattarakasem P, Wangsrimongkol T, Rudee Surarit, Chariya Hahnvajjanawong. *In vitro* and *in vivo* anti- inflammatory potential of *Cryptolepis buchanani*. J ethnopharmacol 2006; 108(2): 349-54.
- 18) Naik S, Singh D, Aggarwal A. Immunomodulatory activity of *Semecarpus anacardium* extract in mononuclear cells of normal individuals and rheumatoid arthritis patients. J ethnopharmacol 2006; 188(3): 398-406.
- 19) Xuefeng Z, Xiaoya Z, Jizhou W et al. Immunomodulatory activity of the Rhizomes of *Impatiens Pritzllii var. hupehensis* on collagen induced arthritis mice. J ethnopharmacol 2007; 109(3):505-09.
- 20) Jeong- EH, Yong-HB, Dong- SP et al. Protective effects of butanol fraction from *Betula platyphyla* var. Japonica on cartilage alterations in a rabbit collagenase-induced osteoarthritis. J ethnopharmacol 2009; 123(3): 515-21.
- 21) Poosarla A, Veerendra B et al. Alleviation of collagen induced arthritis by *Plumbago zeylinica* in mice. Pharmaceutical Bio 2007; 45(1): 54-49.
- 22) Kumar V, Abbas AK, Fausto N. Robbins and Cotran Pathological basic of Disease. 7th ed. Pennsylvania, Elsevier- A division of reed Elsevier: Ind Pvt.Ltd; 2004. p. 1304-08.
- 23) Edward D, Harris MD. Rheumatoid arthritis pathology and implication for therapy. N Eng/J Med 1990; 322(18):1277-88.
- 24) Dr. Kurian JC. Plants that heals. 1st ed. Pune: Oriental watchman publishing House; 1995. p. 144,183.
- 25) Chikanza JC, Jawed S, Naughton D, Blake DR. Why do we need new treatments for rheumatoid arthritis? J Pharma Pharmacol 1998; 50:357-59.
- 26) Sharma PC, Yelne MB, Dennis TJ. Database on medicinal plants used in Ayurveda Vol I. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and siddha; 2000.p.394-95.

- 27) Ambasta SP. The useful plants of India. New Delhi: Publication and Information directorate; CSIR; 1994.p.262.
- 28) Vaidyaratnam Varier PS. Indian medicinal plants-a compendium of 500 species. Vol. III. Madras: Orient Longman Ltd; 1995.p.144-45.
- 29) *Hemidesmus indicus*: ayurvedic herbs- Indian ayurvedic medicines.[Online]. 2006,Suk-YK, Seo-YY et al. The antiarthritic activity effect of ursolic acid on Zymosan induce acute inflammation and adjuvant induced chronic arthritic models. J Pharm Pharmacol 2008; 60:1347-54.
- 30) The wealth of India. Vol-V, Raw Material. New Delhi: CSIR Pub; 2001;33-34.
- 31) Anoop austin. Review on indian Sarsaparilla, *Hemidesmus indicus* (L). R. Br. J Bio Sci 2008; 8(1):1-12.
- 32) Acharya D, Sancheti G, Dr.Shrivastava A, Dr.Pawar S. Rare herb of patalkot: *Hemidismus indicus*. A Chatterjee, Joshi PC. New coumarino-lignoids from *Hemidismus indicus* R.Br. Ind J Chem 1992; 31(B):342-45.
- 33) Roy SK, Ali M, Sharma MP. New pentacyclin triterpines from the roots of *Hemidismus indicus*. Pharmazie2001; 56(3):244-46.
- 34) Rastogi RP, Mehrotra BN. Compendium of Indian medicinal plants Vol-V, Central Drug Research Institute. Lucknow: 1990-1994; 420-21.
- 35) Rastogi RP, Mehrotra BN. Compendium of Indian medicinal plants Vol-II, Central Drug Research Institute. Lucknow.1970-1979.p.364.
- 36) Kumar GS, Jayaveera KN Ashok kumar CK Bharati T. Evaluation of antioxidant and antiacne properties of terpenoidal fraction of *Hemidesmus indicus* Kannabiran K, Mahalingam Gayatri. Hypoglycemic activity of *Hemidesmus indicus* on streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. Int J Diab. 2008; 128:647-57.
- 37) Das S, S Niranjali Devaraj. Effect of *H. indicus* root extract against *Salmonella enterica serovar* Typhimurium-induced apoptosis in murine macrophage cell line(P388D1). Ind J Med Res 2008; 128:647-57.
- 38) Khanna VG, Kannabiran K. Antimicrobial activity of saponin fraction from the roots of *Hemidesmus indicus*. Res J Med Plant 2008; 2(1):39-2.
- 39) Bhadane VV, Patil GG, Mali PY. Collected some traditional herbal formulations in the treatment of rheumatism from Jalgaon district. J Nat Rem 2008; 8(1):48-56.

- 40) Khanna VG, Kannabiran K. Larvicidal effect of aqueous root extract of *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Gymnema sylvestri* and *Eclipta prostrata* against *Culex quinquefasciatus* mosquito larvae. *Afr J Biotech* 2007; 6(3):307-311.
- 41) Previati M, Corbacella E, Astolfi L, Catozzi M, Khan MT, Lampronti I, Gambari R, Capitani S, Martini A. Ethanolic extract from *Hemidesmus indicus* (Linn) displays otoprotectant activities on organotypic cultures without interfering on gentamicin uptake. *J Chem Neuroanat* 2007; 34(3-4):128-33.
- 42) Saravanan N, Rajasankar S, Nalini N. Antioxidant effect of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy Benzoic acid on ethanol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats. *J Pharm Pharmacol* 2007; 59(3):445-53.
- 43) Saravanan N. Impact of *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. extract on ethanol-mediated oxidative damage in rat kidney. *Redox Rep* 2007; 12(5):229-35.
- 44) Kumar GS, Jayaveera KN, Ashok kumar CK et al. antimicrobial effects of Indian medicinal plants against acne producing bacteria. *Trop j pharma res* 2007; 6(2)717-723.
- 45) Purohit HJ, Kainthla RP, Kashyap RS. Effect of HI extract on IgG production and adenosine deaminase activity of human lymphocytes in vitro. *Ind J Pharmacol* 2006; 38(3):190-93.
- 46) Baheti JR, Goyal RK and Shah GB. Hepatoprotective activity of *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. in rats. *Ind J Exp Bio*2006; 44(5):399-402.
- 47) Kotnis MS, Patel P, Menon SN, Sane RT. Renoprotective effect of *Hemidesmus indicus*, a herbal drug used in Gentamicin-induced renal toxicity. *Nephrology (Carlton)*. 2004; 9(3):142-52.
- 48) Gomes A. Snake bite Treatment: a Challenge to Herbal Antagonists. *Ind J Pharmacol* 2004; 36(3):201.
- 49) Fulzele SV, Satturwar PM, Joshi SB, Dorle AK. Studies on Antiinflammatory activity of a Polyherbal formulation Jatyadihrta. *Ind Drugs* 2002; 39(1):42-4.
- 50) Pandye KK, Vandana, Dwivedi M. Urinary tract infection and its management by Renalka. *The Antiseptic* 2001; 98(8):295.
- 51) Ahmed I, Beg A. Antimicrobial and phytochemical studies on 45 Indian medicinal plants against multi drug resistant human pathogens. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2001; 74:113-23.
- 52) Khandelwal KR. *Practical Pharmacognosy, Technique and Experiments*. 9th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2002. p.117-22.

- 53) Khandelwal KR. Practical Pharmacognosy, Techniques and Experiments, 9th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2002. p.9-14.
- 54) Khan ZUR, Assad N, Naeem-ul-Hassan M, et al. Aconitum lycoctonum-mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential. *BMC Chemistry*. 2023;17:128.
- 55) Li MJ, Li CY, Sha MX, et al. Mechanism of *Aconitum pendulum* in rheumatoid arthritis based on toxicity-efficacy evaluation and metabonomics. *Zhongguo Zhong Yao Za Zhi*. 2024;49(7):1774–1784.
- 56) Meng M, Zhao L, Liu W, et al. Effect of polysaccharides from *Aconitum pendulum* on rheumatoid arthritis. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2025;331:148405.
- 57) Kim JH, et al. Anti-rheumatic and analgesic effects of *Aconitum jaluense* tubers in arthritis-induced rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2022;289:114518.
- 58) Gupta R, Saxena R, Malviya N. Anti-inflammatory activity of ethanolic extract of *Aconitum napellus* against carrageenan-induced paw edema. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*. 2019.